

Research Article

Personal experience and professional commitment to recommended vaccines in the Pleven district

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Summary

Introduction: According to the current regulations of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Bulgaria, the administration of the recommended vaccines is implemented at the request of the patient and for a fee. In this context, one of the key functions of the general practitioners (GPs) within the framework of outpatient primary care is to conduct health prevention, including the performance of immunizations. In 2024, the number of general practitioners in the Pleven district with a contract with the National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) was 176.

Objective: The objective of the study was to assess the influence of general practitioners' personal experience and commitment on the implementation and promotion of recommended vaccinations.

Materials and methods: In 2024, a comprehensive survey was carried out in the Pleven district covering 82 general practitioner selected at random from a total of 176 registered in the region. To analyse the correlation between the qualitative variables, a χ^2 test was applied, with statistical conclusions drawn at a significance level of 0.05. Data collection was performed through semi-structured interview and processed by SPSS Statistics v.26.

Results: Data analysis revealed high vaccination coverage among the respondents – 75 (91.5%), as well as significant activity in recommending the additional immunizations – 80 (97.6%). The personal experience with the recommended vaccines had an important impact on the professional behaviour of medical professionals ($\chi^2 = 21.964$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$, Cramer's $V = 0.518$).

Conclusion: The present study outlined the significant influence of personal experience with the recommended immunizations on the professional behaviour of general practitioners. That highlighted the need to increase awareness and personal commitment to vaccination among healthcare professionals as a key factor in improving vaccination coverage of the population.

Key words: Professional commitment, recommended vaccines, GP

Introduction

Vaccination is one of the most reliable and cost-effective public health interventions worldwide. However, growing distrust in science, combined with the spread of misinformation, has led to a decline in vaccination coverage in

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specific communities (BMA 2022). In Bulgaria, the Ministry of Health is responsible for developing and implementing the national health policy. Its priorities include ensuring the supply of high-quality vaccines against socially significant and life-threatening diseases, maintaining comprehensive immunisation coverage, and protecting the population from vaccine-preventable conditions (NHIF).

The National Health Insurance Fund (NHIF) monitors and supervises the implementation of vaccination activities. General practitioners (GPs) contracted to provide primary outpatient medical care serve as leading providers (NHIF 2024).

According to Article 1 of Ordinance No. 15 of 12 May 2005, on immunisations in the Republic of Bulgaria, the categories of individuals subject to mandatory, targeted, and recommended immunisations and re-immunisations are clearly defined. Recommended immunisations and re-immunisations are carried out at a patient's request and expense. Exceptions are made when these are covered under national programmes, which also include administration costs (Ordinance amending and supplementing Ordinance No. 15 of 2005 on immunisations in the Republic of Bulgaria 2005).

By 2024, three preventive vaccination programmes were operating in Bulgaria. These include vaccines against cervical cancer for girls aged 10 to 13, vaccines against rotavirus gastroenteritis primarily for children over six weeks old, and vaccines against seasonal influenza and pneumococcal infections for people aged 65 and above (Betsch et al. 2018).

The National Programme for Primary Prevention of Cancers Caused by Human Papillomavirus (HPV) 2025–2030 extends free vaccination rights to girls aged 10–14, thus increasing the eligibility period by one year compared to the previous programme. Starting in 2025, boys will also be eligible for free HPV vaccination. From 2025 to 2028, vaccines will be available to boys aged 10 to 13 years old. In 2029–2030, eligibility will be expanded to include 14-year-old boys. Furthermore, between 2025 and 2028, the programme will expand to include girls aged 15–17. In its final two years (2029–2030), eligibility will also be extended to women aged 18 to 21.

Research shows that parents generally trust healthcare professionals' advice, especially GPs, about vaccination, despite the exposure to contradictory and often misleading information from other sources (Chalkidou et al. 2012).

According to the Law on Medical Establishments, providers of primary outpatient medical care may set up individual or group practices (Law on Medical Institutions 1999). Within these practices, they carry out their professional activities. One of their primary functions is to protect and promote the health of their patients through preventive healthcare, vaccination being a crucial part of primary prevention (Dahlgren and Whitehead 1991).

As of 2024, 3,401 GPs are working under contract with the NHIF in Bulgaria. Their distribution across the 28 administrative regions is uneven. The Pleven region, comprising 11 municipalities, reported 176 GPs during the same study period.

The study aimed to explore how personal experience and professional engagement of general practitioners affect their adoption and advocacy of recommended vaccines.

Materials and methods

In 2024, a medico-social study was carried out in the Pleven region to investigate how general practitioners (GPs) approach recommended vaccinations, the challenges they encounter, and how their personal attitudes and behaviours influence vaccination practices.

Our study includes 88 general practitioners (50%, every other one out of the 176 in the Pleven region). The response rate achieved was 93.2% (82 out of 88 GPs).

Data were collected through individual semi-structured interviews, using a specially designed questionnaire approved by the Research Ethics Committee at the Medical University of Pleven (Ref. No. 807 KENID/14.06.2024).

The statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS Statistics version 26. Cramer's V coefficient was utilised to assess statistically significant associations between variables. In contrast, the χ^2 test was employed to identify significant differences between groups.

Results and discussion

The study investigated how individual attitudes, professional experience, and awareness of medical specialists affected their behaviour when consulting patients about vaccine prophylaxis. Among the 82 general practitioners surveyed in the Pleven district, 67 (81.7%) practised independently, while 15 (18.3%) worked in group practices. The dominance of the individual model emphasises the limited opportunities for multidisciplinary collaboration and knowledge sharing. The absence of group practice structures may impede the integration of other professionals, such as psychologists and social workers, whose input is vital for strengthening public health. These findings align with data from the Bulgarian Medical Association, which highlights the high level of fragmentation within primary healthcare in Bulgaria (BMA 2022).

The study included a total of 82 general practitioners (GPs) from 11 municipalities in the Pleven region. The largest group was from Pleven municipality, comprising fifty-six general practitioners, which represented 68.3% of the sample. The rest of the participants from other municipalities in the region were as follows: Levski – 9 participants (11.0%), Belene – 6 participants (7.3%), Dolna Mitropolia – 5 participants (6.1%), and Dolni Dabnik and Kneja – 6 participants (7.3%), with three from each.

Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

The gender distribution showed a predominance of women, with 53 participants accounting for 64.6%, compared to 29 men at 35.4% ($\chi^2 = 7.024$; $p = 0.011$), indicating that women were more prominently represented in this speciality.

Most respondents were over 50 years old, comprising 63 individuals (76.8%) of the sample. The most numerous age group was 50 to 60 years, with 33 participants (40.2%), followed by the 40 to 50 years age group with 30 participants (36.6%). Younger age groups were underrepresented, with only 8 participants (9.8%) aged 30 to 40, and 11 participants (13.4%) aged 40 to 50. The chi-square test showed a significant difference ($\chi^2 = 24.049$; $p < 0.001$), indicating an ageing workforce and a potential risk of staff shortages in the near future, which

aligns with WHO reports highlighting the urgent need to rejuvenate healthcare systems (Dobbins et al. 2004).

Regarding the type of practice, individual practices were clearly dominant, with 67 participants (81.7%) involved compared to 15 participants (18.3%) engaged in group practice ($\chi^2 = 32.976$; $p < 0.001$). The dominance of the individual model indicates limited opportunities for multidisciplinary collaboration and knowledge exchange. The absence of group practice structures may impede the integration of other professionals, such as psychologists and social workers, whose roles are essential for public health. These findings align with the Bulgarian Medical Association, emphasising the high level of fragmentation in primary healthcare (BMA 2022).

Analysis of professional experience showed that more than two-thirds of respondents had extensive practice. A total of 55 participants, or 67.1%, reported having over 25 years of professional experience. Among them, 23 participants (28.0%) had 35 years of experience, 22 participants (26.8%) had 25 years, and 10 participants (12.2%) had 30 years of experience. Fewer respondents reported shorter experience: 5 participants (6.1%) had up to 5 years, 7 participants (8.5%) had 10 years, 5 participants (6.1%) had 15 years, and 10 participants (12.2%) had 20 years of experience ($\chi^2 = 30.000$; $p < 0.001$). These findings confirm the accumulation of significant professional capital, further emphasising the need for strategies to guarantee continuity, attract young specialists, and establish mentorship models.

Analysis of professional activities of GPs

The analysis of professional activities by general practitioners (GPs) in the Pleven region revealed a primary emphasis on preventive and chronic care. The most common task was health prevention, reported by 62 respondents, representing 75.6% of cases. The second most common activity involved clinical examinations of patients with chronic conditions, reported by 55 (67.1%) of the respondents. These findings underscore the crucial role of GPs in both preventing and managing chronic diseases, as integral components of primary healthcare (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Professional activities performed by GPs (N = 234).

A total of 40 respondents (48.8%) reported conducting treatment activities, while 30 respondents (36.6%) focused on children's healthcare. Health promotion was pointed out by 19 respondents (23.2%), and screening for socially significant diseases was noted by 17 respondents (20.7%). Only seven respondents (8.5%) emphasised maternal health, and four respondents (4.9%) reported engaging in other types of activities.

Seventy-seven physicians, representing 93.9% of the sample, reported possessing sound knowledge of primary prevention components. Nevertheless, despite this self-assessment, the majority of general practitioners (GPs) primarily focused on general health prevention, with fewer engaging in maternal health and targeted screening. This gap highlights a lack of integration of comprehensive preventive services and points to the need for more explicit role definitions in health promotion, updated training in screening for chronic and mental illnesses, and stronger collaboration with NGOs and public health experts. Moreover, only 48.8% of respondents stated that they had sufficient time for health promotion activities, revealing a discrepancy between their theoretical preparedness and their actual practice—an issue also underscored by previous research (Kringos et al. 2015).

Analysis of the role of GPs in primary prevention and health promotion

Most respondents, i.e., 81 physicians (98.8%), regarded GPs as key players in primary prevention and health promotion. Other healthcare professionals were less frequently mentioned, including 50 physicians (61.0%) who pointed to other specialists, and 29 physicians (35.4%) who named public health experts. The involvement of NGOs and universities was minimal, with only seven responses (8.5%) and four responses (4.9%), respectively. This pattern highlights the dominance of a mono-professional approach in Bulgaria and the limited recognition of intersectoral collaborations, a common issue noted in several European studies (WHO 2022).

The assessment of immunisation coverage and preventive check-ups by GPs in the Pleven region reveals clear distinctions between mandatory and recommended activities. Coverage for mandatory immunisations, as per the national schedule, was rated as very positive, with 59 physicians (72.0%) describing it as “a lot of good” and 23 physicians (28.0%) as “good.” No respondents found this activity unsatisfactory (Fig. 2).

A strong association was found between the GPs' personal uptake of recommended vaccines and their willingness to recommend them to patients ($\chi^2 = 21.964$; $p < 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.518$), suggesting that doctors' own vaccination practices significantly influence patient attitudes and behaviours, aligning with the findings of Betsch et al. (Betsch et al. 2018).

In contrast, the coverage with recommended immunisations was significantly lower. Only 26 physicians (31.7%) rated it as “very good,” while 38 physicians (46.3%) considered it “good.” Importantly, 17 physicians (20.7%) viewed coverage as merely “satisfactory,” and one physician (1.2%) found it unsatisfactory. These results suggest specific challenges in implementing recommended vaccines relative to compulsory ones.

A significant statistical link was found between immunisation coverage and age group and professional experience ($\chi^2 = 12.171$; $p = 0.007$), indicating that demographic and professional backgrounds influence immunisation practices.

Figure 2. Assessment of immunisation coverage and preventive exams by general practitioners.

These results align with those of Wiysonge et al. (Wiysonge et al. 2021), who state that physicians' personal commitment and experience influence their vaccine recommendations.

Preventive examinations for children up to 18 years old received predominantly positive feedback, with 54 physicians (65.9%) rating them as "very good" and 24 physicians (29.3%) as "good." Only three physicians (3.7%) found them "satisfactory," and one physician (1.2%) regarded them as unsatisfactory. This feedback rating reflects excellent performance in paediatric preventive care.

Among patients over 18, evaluations were less favourable. Thirty-seven doctors (45.1%) rated preventive exams as "very good," while 35 (42.7%) viewed them as "good." Eight doctors (9.8%) considered them "satisfactory," and 2 (2.4%) found them unsatisfactory. The lower ratings for adult preventive exams highlight a need for increased attention and resources in this area.

Overall, the results showed that compulsory immunisations and paediatric preventive care were highly regarded. However, recommended immunisations and adult preventive visits were less frequently conducted. This gap highlights systemic issues in preventive healthcare that require targeted efforts, particularly to increase vaccination coverage and improve preventive services for adults.

The majority of respondents, totalling 62 (75.6%), cited the absence of financial incentives for general practitioners (GPs) as the main reason for low vaccination rates. As shown in Fig. 3, this highlights a fundamental systemic issue within primary care organisations, where activities such as administering recommended vaccines are not compensated, making them less of a priority on a daily basis. This situation highlights the limitations of the current capitation model and the need for supplementary incentives to encourage preventive care. Evidence from around the world suggests that implementing performance-based payments can significantly increase vaccination coverage, particularly for recommended but non-mandatory vaccines (World Health Organisation 2025).

In second and third place, respondents emphasised behavioural factors common in communities with limited health literacy. Forty-seven physicians (57.3%) identified insufficient patient awareness as a significant barrier, while

Figure 3. Main factors for low vaccination coverage among patients according to GPs.

forty-three physicians (52.4%) cited patients' lack of trust. These factors highlight hesitant attitudes toward vaccination, driven by ongoing disinformation, low health literacy, the influence of anti-vaccination media, and the absence of a consistent governmental communication strategy. The problem is especially urgent with recommended vaccines, which are not legally mandatory and lack clear public messaging from authorities. Our results also align with international studies (Betsch et al. 2018) and demonstrate that awareness and trust are key factors influencing immunisation behaviour.

On an operational level, 17 respondents (20.9%) cited limited consultation time as a barrier to discussing vaccination with patients. This issue is understandable given the heavy workloads and short appointment durations. Even when physicians aim to inform patients, time and organisational constraints often prevent them from doing so. Furthermore, 15 respondents (18.3%) reported communication difficulties between doctors and patients as another obstacle. These answers reflected limited interaction opportunities and highlighted the need for improved health-related communication skills. According to recent behavioural medicine research, the lack of clear, persuasive and accessible communication increases vaccine hesitancy and refusals. These issues emphasise the importance of practical training for GPs in micro-interventions and brief, effective communication strategies that combine empathy, factual accuracy, and simple language (WHO Behavioural Insights Unit 2022).

As illustrated in Fig. 4, 75 respondents (91.5%) reported having received the recommended vaccinations, while seven respondents (8.5%) had not. Additionally, 80 respondents, accounting for 97.6%, stated they recommend vaccination to their patients; however, only five respondents, or 6.1% of the non-vaccinated group, would make such a recommendation. A highly significant association exists between GPs' personal vaccination status and their likelihood to recommend vaccines to patients ($\chi^2 = 21.964$; $p < 0.001$; Cramer's $V = 0.518$).

These findings reinforce the notion that leading by personal example is key in influencing patients' health behaviours (Betsch et al. 2018).

Figure 4. Personal experience and professional commitment of healthcare professionals regarding recommended vaccinations.

This association highlights the concept of “model behaviour”, where a physician’s personal health choices influence patient trust and willingness to follow medical advice. Data support International findings suggest that healthcare workers who are vaccinated are more likely to recommend immunisation, doing so more convincingly with stronger arguments (Betsch et al. 2018; WHO 2022). In this regard, the preventive mindset of healthcare professionals can be seen as a strategic asset in efforts to boost vaccination rates nationwide.

The analysis revealed several statistically significant relationships between the examined indicators. Notably, a significant correlation was found between mandatory immunisation coverage and preventive check-ups for patients under 18 ($\chi^2 = 12.171$, $df = 3$, $p = 0.007$, Cramer’s $V = 0.385$), indicating a connection between these two aspects of preventive care. A similar relationship was found for patients over 18, with immunisation coverage and check-ups showing a significant association ($\chi^2 = 18.366$, $df = 3$, $p < 0.001$, Cramer’s $V = 0.473$).

The link between recommended immunisations and preventive activities was also highly significant (e.g., $\chi^2 = 36.510$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.001$, Cramer’s $V = 0.385$), highlighting the interconnectedness of preventive health services. These results suggest that higher vaccination rates are associated with improved preventive check-up indicators across all age groups.

The analysis of socio-demographic traits revealed a significant correlation between respondents’ age and their years of professional experience ($\chi^2 = 54.167$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.001$, Cramer’s $V = 0.469$), indicating that age is positively associated with professional experience. Regarding patients’ mental health, we found that physicians involved in health prevention, follow-up care, or health promotion tended to rate their patients’ mental health as good or very good ($\chi^2 = 61.665$, $df = 40$, $p = 0.015$), emphasising the role of preventive efforts in supporting population mental well-being.

The link between understanding primary prevention components and the ability to evaluate mental health was also statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 7.202$, $df = 2$, $p = 0.027$, Cramer’s $V = 0.296$), highlighting the importance of knowledge

transfer and sharing best practices in these areas. Similar significant relationships were observed between the availability of time for health promotion, knowledge of risk factors, and skills in working with vulnerable groups, all with high statistical significance ($\chi^2 = 35.910$, $df = 9$, $p < 0.001$, Cramer's $V = 0.382$).

Overall, our results not only established statistically significant relationships between key variables in applied public health but also highlighted the importance of strategic knowledge transfer and best practices within the primary healthcare system.

According to data from the Regional Health Inspectorate (RHI) – Pleven, several recommended immunisations and re-immunisations had been reported by 2024.

According to reports from general practitioners (GPs), 68 people received seasonal influenza vaccines purchased by themselves in 2024, down from 85 in 2023. In 2024, 17,290 individuals were vaccinated under the Ministry of Health's National Program, an increase from 15,704 in the previous year. The goal for 2024 was to vaccinate 27% of people aged 65 and older; in the Pleven district, the coverage reached 27.6%.

Under the National Program, 3,251 individuals aged 65 and older received pneumococcal vaccines provided by the Ministry of Health. The 2024 target was 5% coverage of the 65+ age group, with the Pleven district expected to reach a 5.18% rate.

In 2024, HPV vaccine coverage among 12- and 13-year-olds in Pleven rose by 40% compared to 2023. Of the 12-year-olds, 201 received the first dose and 103 received the second dose, as per the two-dose schedule. Among 13-year-olds, 113 received the first dose and 86 received the second. Additionally, 120 people outside the target age groups were vaccinated in 2024, up from only 13 in 2023.

In the two-dose rotavirus vaccination schedule, 614 individuals received the first dose and 554 received the second dose, consistent with 2023 levels. For the three-dose schedule, 312 individuals received the first dose, 301 the second, and 262 the third, marking a 17% rise from the previous year.

In 2024, 82 individuals in the Pleven district received the varicella vaccine, up from 38 in 2023 (Katon et al. 2007).

At the national level, there are no official statistical data on the recommended immunisations given in primary care. However, GPs play a crucial role. Dismissing parents' concerns or providing weak responses, along with low vaccination rates among GPs themselves, can significantly harm future vaccine demand and influence the use of other health services. Personal experience and professional dedication, based on clear communication and trust with parents, are crucial for reducing perceived barriers to immunisation.

In most regions, people with high trust in their GP are much more likely to believe vaccines are safe, although this effect is weaker in Western and Eastern Europe. Additionally, a positive link exists between general trust in science and trust in vaccines, with this connection being strongest in high-income countries.

Conclusion

This study reaffirmed the importance of general practitioners (GPs) in enhancing preventive healthcare and increasing vaccine coverage in Bulgaria. Vaccination is among the most cost-effective public health measures; however, obstacles such as misinformation, limited health literacy, and systemic issues

still hinder its widespread uptake. In the Pleven region, findings showed that although mandatory immunisations and paediatric preventive care are effectively provided, the recommended immunisations and preventive services for adults are still not adequately implemented.

Our findings highlighted several key factors. Firstly, GPS's professional experience and personal attitudes significantly influence their willingness to recommend vaccines. Doctors who personally received recommended immunisations were more inclined to advise their patients similarly, offering more compelling reasons. Their behaviour highlights the role of "model behaviour," where personal example fosters patient trust and encourages compliance. Secondly, systemic issues such as the absence of financial incentives and the dominance of individual over group practices limit opportunities for interprofessional collaboration and the integration of preventive care. Thirdly, behavioural barriers, including low patient awareness, a lack of trust, and communication challenges during brief consultations, further hinder vaccine uptake.

The statistical analysis supported these findings, showing strong links between vaccination coverage, preventive exams, and the practitioners' socio-demographic traits. Preventive activities were also favourably associated with their understanding of primary prevention, professional involvement, and the ability to assess patients' mental health, thus indicating that preventive practices are both multifaceted and interconnected.

The study emphasises an urgent need at the policy level to strengthen Bulgaria's primary care system. Key actions should include: (i) increasing access to vaccines, such as providing free or subsidised vaccines for healthcare workers; (ii) implementing financial incentives based on performance to boost preventive care; (iii) funding training in advanced screening techniques and health communication; and (iv) fostering collaboration across sectors with NGOs, public health specialists, and universities.

In summary, Bulgarian GPs show a strong dedication to mandatory immunisations and children's preventive care. However, significant challenges still hinder the implementation of recommended immunisations and adult preventive services. To achieve enhanced vaccination coverage and protect public health regionally and nationally, it is crucial to foster a preventive culture among healthcare professionals, allocate sufficient resources, and address systemic barriers to vaccination.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed oral and written consent was obtained from all participants and confidentiality was strictly observed.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

All authors contributed equally to the concept of the article. Writing – original draft: Writing – review and editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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